

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT: COUMARINS

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The dielectric constant and density of coumarin have been measured in the molten state at various temperatures. The dielectric constants and densities of coumarin 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetyl- and 4-methyl-8-acetyl-umbelliferones have been measured in solution at various concentrations and temperatures. The moments have been calculated by applying the new equation and the values obtained compared with the values calculated theoretically.

The simplest derivative of α -pyrone is the benzo- α -pyrone or coumarin. The moment of this compound has been determined by a number of workers. The values obtained by different workers are shown below.

TABLE I

Solvent.	Temp.	$\mu_{\text{obs.}}$	μ_{new}	Authors.
Benzene	15-65°	4.54	...	Syrkin ¹ & Vasilev
Benzene	10-40°	4.51	3.78	Govinda Rao ²
Benzene	25°	4.48	...	LeFevre ³ & LeFevre
Dioxane	30-40°	...	3.85	Miss Kulkarni ⁴
Molten liquid	70-159°	...	4.89	Miss Kulkarni ⁴
Benzene	20-45°	4.56	3.82	Present work

1. Syrkin & Vasilev, *Acta Physicochem. U.R.S.S.*, 1937, 6, 639.

2. Govinda Rao, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 4A, 687.

3. LeFevre, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1088, 1937.

4. Miss Kulkarni, A.I.I.Sc. Thesis, Bangalore

In the present work, along with coumarin, the moments of 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetyl- and 4-methyl-8-acetyl-umbelliferones have been measured in benzene solution over a temperature range of 25-45°. The moments of the latter two compounds have been determined for the first time. The results are shown in Tables II-V.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Thiophene-free benzene was purified as described in a previous paper (this *issue*, p. 1). The portion that froze at 5.5° was finally distilled over phosphorus pentoxide.

Coumarin, 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetyl-, and 4-methyl-8-acetyl-umbelliferones were recrystallised from alcohol till the observed melting points agreed with the literature,

TABLE IIA*

Coumarin.

(a) Solvent: benzene. $P_x = 159.9$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ
	$w_2 = 0.035493$				$w_2 = 0.054692$				$w_2 = 0.073176$			
20°	2.874	0.88739	2890	3.82	3.205	0.89445	2887	3.82	3.605	0.90041	2855	3.80
25°	2.852	0.88198	2849	3.82	3.174	0.88868	2850	3.82	3.571	0.89441	2862	3.81
30°	2.830	0.87666	2812	3.83	3.143	0.88277	2816	3.83	3.538	0.88855	2796	3.82
35°	2.808	0.87050	2776	3.83	3.112	0.87657	2765	3.83	3.504	0.88260	2763	3.82
40°	2.786	0.86469	2734	3.83	3.081	0.87035	2719	3.82	3.472	0.87658	2735	3.83
45°	2.764	0.85889	2697	3.84	3.049	0.86413	2675	3.82	3.440	0.87061	2709	3.84

 $n_D^{20} = 1.50453$; $n_D^{25} = 1.4954$; $n_D^{30} = 1.4855$; $n_D^{35} = 1.4757$; $n_D^{40} = 1.4647$; $n_D^{45} = 1.4558$.

* Present work.

TABLE IIB

TABLE IIC

(b) Molten liquid. (Miss Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*). Solvent: dioxane (Miss Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*).

Temp.	ϵ	d	P	μ_{new}	Temp.	w_2	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
150°	26.13	1.1199	3279.3	4.88	30°	0.1239	4.615	1.0446	2847.0	3.80
125°	28.18	1.1396	3485.5	4.89		0.1323	4.805	1.0466	2869.4	3.84
110°	29.67	1.1519	3637.3	4.93		0.1382	4.866	1.0467	2917.7	3.95
91°	31.40	1.1666	3808.2	4.89	40°	0.1239	4.509	1.0339	2768.3	3.84
70°	34.04	1.1834	4080.2	4.86		0.1323	4.684	1.0344	2788.7	3.85
						0.1382	4.792	1.0349	2785.5	3.85

TABLE IID

Solvent: benzene (Govinda Rau, *loc. cit.*).

f_2	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
	Temp. = 10°.				Temp. = 20°.			
0.0000	2.299	0.8881	...	...	2.279	0.8774	...	...
0.01579	2.490	0.8909	2955	3.80	2.462	0.8803	2850	3.82
0.00918	2.590	0.8926	2952	3.80	2.558	0.8821	2872	3.80
0.01440	2.757	0.8949	2958	3.80	2.716	0.8845	2872	3.80
0.01748	2.856	0.8967	2975	3.81	2.811	0.8861	2875	3.81
	Temp. = 30°.				Temp. = 40°.			
0.00000	2.260	0.8667	...	...	2.241	0.8560	...	...
0.00599	2.434	0.8697	2771	3.80	2.406	0.8591	2655	3.78
0.00918	2.525	0.8715	2746	3.76	2.493	0.8609	2669	3.78
0.01440	2.676	0.8740	2764	3.79	2.635	0.8635	2645	3.77
0.01748	2.765	0.8755	2774	3.80	2.721	0.8659	2677	3.79

 $\mu_D^{10} = 1.50450$; $\mu_D^{20} = 1.4951$; $\mu_D^{30} = 1.4852$; $\mu_D^{40} = 1.4752$

TABLE III*

4-Methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylbulliferone.

Solvent: benzene.

 $P_2 = 268.96.$

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
25°	5.360	0.8784	2194	3.32	2.393	0.8806	2281	3.31	2.415	0.8817	2346	3.36
30°	2.350	0.8727	2336	3.38	2.384	0.8742	2342	3.39	2.404	0.8753	2373	3.41
35°	2.340	0.8654	2402	3.46	2.375	0.8674	2390	3.45	2.393	0.8687	2387	3.45
40°	2.330	0.8590	2445	3.53	2.364	0.8612	2405	3.49	2.370	0.8523	2387	3.48
45°	2.320	0.8526	2488	3.59	2.357	0.8546	2498	3.60	2.370	0.8557	2429	3.54

TABLE IV*

4-Methyl-8-acetylbulliferone.

Solvent: benzene.

 $P_2 = 232.0.$

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
25°	2.349	0.8760	2271	3.33	2.382	0.8770	2271	3.33	2.416	0.8784	2282	3.34
30°	2.337	0.8709	2247	3.34	2.369	0.8720	2238	3.33	2.404	0.8734	2257	3.35
35°	2.328	0.8660	2200	3.33	2.359	0.8653	2221	3.34	2.392	0.8684	2218	3.34
40°	2.317	0.8610	2175	3.33	2.347	0.8618	2171	3.33	2.379	0.8636	2167	3.32
45°	2.306	0.8560	2127	3.32	2.336	0.8568	2137	3.32	2.369	0.8588	2141	3.33

* Present work

TABLE V

Moments.

Compound.	Solvent.	μ_{new}		$\mu_{calc.}$	μ_{DC}
		1kT.	1.5kT.		
Coumarin	Molten ^a	4.89		5.08	
	Dioxane ^a	(3.85)	4.72		
	Benzene ^b	(3.78)	4.63		4.51
	Benzene ^c	(3.82)	4.63		4.56
4-Methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylbulliferone	Benzene ^c	3.33—3.58		3.78	
	25-45°	(3.75)			
4-Methyl-8-acetylbulliferone	Benzene ^c	(3.33)	4.08	3.78	

a. Miss Kulkarni, *loc. cit.*b. Govinda Rao, *loc. cit.*

c. Present work.

DISCUSSION

Coumarin

The Debye moment of coumarin in solution is 4.51–4.56. Recalculation of the data of Govinda Rao (*loc. cit.*) by the application of the new equation gives a moment of 3.78. The new moment in dioxane is 3.85 and in molten state the value is 4.89. The present measurements in benzene solution provide a value of 3.82 for the moment of coumarin. All these values are summarised in the table of moments.

It appears from these values that in solution there is a decrease in hindered rotation which increases $2j + 1 = 2$ (1kT) to $2j + 1 = 3$ (1.5kT). Effectively, the moment in solution

will be increased to a value of 4.72 which compares with moment 4.89, obtained in molten state.

The moment of coumarin can be calculated theoretically as follows. Coumarin resonates between structures (I) and (II).

Structure (I): C-O (1) and C-O (2) affect each other inductively and each is reduced to a moment value of 0.74. The moment along C=O will be 3.64. This together with a moment of 0.74 of C-O (1) gives the resultant molecular moment, the value of which is 3.33.

Structure (II): C-O (1) and C-O (2), each, have a moment of 1.48. The induction effect is negligible. The moment along C-O (1) is 2.96. This adds up vectorially with the moment of C=O and gives a value of 5.08 for the molecular moment.

The moment in solution can be increased to a value of 4.72 by increasing $2j+1=2$ ($1kT$) to $2j+1=3$ ($1.5kT$). This value compares with the value calculated for structure (II) and also with value observed in the molten state.

4-Methyl-8-acetylbulliferone

The moment of 4-methyl 8 acetylbulliferone, in benzene solution, has been determined for the first time. The moment calculated by the new equation is 3.33, which is independent of concentration and temperature.

In all these structures C=O (I) and C=O (II) remain unaffected and have a moment of 2.90 each. C-O (I) is reduced to a value of 0.74 because of induction from C-O (II). The effect of C-O (III) is negligible. C-O (II) is reduced to a value of 0.555 because of induction from C-O (I) and C-O (III). C-O (III) gets no effect from C-O (I), but is affected by C-O (II). The resultant moment of C-O (III) is 1.295.

Structure (I): The moment along C₇-C₈ is 6.355 and that along C-O (III) is 2.035. The resultant of the two will be 5.620. This together with the moment of the O-H bond gives the molecular moment, the value of which is 8.004.

Structure (II): The moment along C₇-C₈ is 3.455 and that along C-O (III) is 4.935. The resultant moment is 4.385. This adds up vectorially with the moment 2.4 of the O-H bond and gives the value of 5.779 for the molecular moment.

Structure (III): The moments along C₇-C₈ and C=O (III) are 6.355 and 2.035 respectively. The resultant of these two is 5.620 which with the moment of 2.4 of the O-H bond gives the molecular moment of 3.776.

Structure (IV): The moment along C₇-C₈ is 3.455 and that along C-O (III) is 4.935. The resultant of the two is 4.385. This adds up vectorially with the moment 2.4 of the O-H bond and gives a value of 2.516 for the molecular moment.

The observed moment of 3.33 for 4-methyl-8-acetylbulliferone may be increased to a value of 4.08 by increasing $2j + 1 = 2$ ($1kT$) to $2j + 1 = 3$ ($1.5kT$). This value compares with the calculated value of 3.78 for structure (III).

4-Methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylbulliferone

The moment of 4-methyl-6-ethyl-8-acetylbulliferone in benzene solution has been measured for the first time. The moment obtained by applying the new equation is independent of concentration, but varies with temperature, the value being 3.33 to 3.58 over the temperature range of 25-45°. The possible structures of the compound are

The calculations of the moments are similar to those for 4-methyl-8-acetylbulliferone and the values are : structure (I) - 8.004 ; structure (II) - 5.779 ; structure (III) - 3.776 ; structure (IV) - 2.516. The moments for structures (I) and (II) are very high.

It appears that both structures (III) and (IV) contribute to the molecular moment. The variation of the moment with temperature indicates that the contribution of structure (III) increases with increase of temperature due to the breaking of hydrogen bond. At higher temperature the value of 3.75 is reached asymptotically. This compares with the value calculated for structure (III).

The observed and calculated moments of coumarin, 8-acetyl-4-methylumbelliferone and 8-acetyl-4-methyl-6-ethylumbelliferone are summarised in table of moments.

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